

Integrated Framework for Enhanced Diabetic Patient Care with Predictive Analytics

Lakshima Silva
Faculty of Computing
Sri Lanka Institute of Information
Technology
Malabe, Sri Lanka
lakshimarasanjalee286@gmail.com

Nishedi Fernando
Faculty of Computing
Sri Lanka Institute of Information
Technology
Malabe, Sri Lanka
nishedi5@gmail.com

Pevinya Peiris
Faculty of Computing
Sri Lanka Institute of Information
Technology
Malabe, Sri Lanka
pevinyapeiris@gmail.com

Yeheni Chamoda
Faculty of Computing
Sri Lanka Institute of Information
Technology
Malabe, Sri Lanka
yehenicham240@gmail.com

Kapila Dissanayaka
Faculty of Computing
Sri Lanka Institute of Information
Technology
Malabe, Sri Lanka
kapila.d@sliit.lk

Poojani Gunathilake
Faculty of Computing
Sri Lanka Institute of Information
Technology
Malabe, Sri Lanka
poojani.g@sliit.lk

Abstract—Effective management of Type 2 diabetes and prediabetes requires continuous monitoring and proactive care. However, it is common that patients lapse in monitoring their blood glucose levels, medications, and lifestyle activities. This challenge is particularly evident in countries where accessible digital health solutions are limited. To fill this gap, we have created a mobile app that provides personalized diabetes management by using predictive analytics for blood glucose forecasting, medication adherence, and AI-powered food recognition with calorie estimation. The system also provides real-time tracking of BMI, blood pressure, and heart rate, and AI-powered evaluation for diabetic foot ulcer risk. An SOS alert system is also provided for use during emergencies. Experimental findings validate the system's high performance, achieving 93.3% accuracy for hyperglycemia risk prediction, 91.1% accuracy for activity recommendation, 90.3% accuracy for food classification, and 91.54% accuracy for foot ulcer risk stage prediction. Through the integration of these features within an easy-to-use interface, the app reinforces patients' proactive health management and quality of life.

Keywords—Diabetes Management, Predictive Analytics, AI-Powered Health Monitoring, Mobile Application, Personalized Care

I. INTRODUCTION

Diabetes management has improved significantly with the development in healthcare infrastructure, predictive analytics, and real-time tracking [1]. Traditional practices such as manual noting and check-up episodically often lack continuous tracking, which increases the chances of developing complications. As diabetes is a long-term illness, patients must have their blood sugar levels monitored continuously, their feet taken care of, and their lifestyle checked to prevent severe conditions, such as diabetic foot complications, which, if not identified, can lead to infections and amputations. Predictive analytics and machine learning models have the potential for early detection and timely intervention [2].

Despite rising diabetes incidence, healthcare systems globally cannot provide personalized care due to the lack of real-time feedback and communication lag with patients and providers [3]. Overcoming these deficits, DiabeCare is a smart, centralized smartphone app that integrates health tracking, predictive analytics, and automated notifications to facilitate ongoing monitoring, risk detection, and early

intervention. By offering real-time data, the app aims to improve patient outcomes and reduce complications.

DiabeCare provides Type 2 diabetic and prediabetic patients with total management with key features like blood glucose monitoring, physical activity tracking, and machine learning-based foot complication risk prediction. It also employs high-end image processing and AI-powered food recognition with calorie estimation so that users can be given personalized nutritional guidance. Further, the app monitors basic life health parameters like blood pressure, heart rate, and BMI for effective disease management. These aspects make DiabeCare an integrated and innovative solution for diabetes management. This paper explores AI-based diabetes management, addresses ongoing research, and introduces DiabeCare as an integrated solution that incorporates significant health indicators.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Diabetes control involves many aspects, including the approximation of food calories, monitoring of glucose levels, management of diet, and tracking of activity levels, all of which are very vital for glycemic control. As diabetes becomes more prevalent worldwide, mobile health apps have been showing promise in enhancing patient adherence and outcomes. Yet, issues of accuracy, user commitment, and integration into systems take away from their usefulness. Progress in artificial intelligence (AI), computer vision, and machine learning (ML) is revolutionizing diabetes management through automated and precise solutions. Specifically, deep learning models, i.e., Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), facilitate food image recognition and calorie estimation, overcoming constraints of manual recording and enhancing cultural adaptability via heterogeneous datasets [4].

Blood glucose monitoring is still a foundation of diabetes management, and continuous glucose monitors provide feedback in real time. Yet, they usually have partial integration with dietary and exercise monitoring, which reduces their usefulness. Physical activity monitoring is also important, and mobile applications now use gamification, artificial intelligence-driven exercise routines, and wearable fitness monitors to improve compliance and track vital signs [5]. Despite these advances, the majority of the programs are standalone, not integrating dietary, glucose, and activity data within a comprehensive system.

An integrated AI-based platform that includes diet management, glucose monitoring, and physical activity management has the potential to transform self-management by tackling the multi-component nature of diabetes care in a holistic manner. Integrated AI-based platforms have shown potential in managing complex chronic diseases by combining predictive models, dietary guidance, and medical resource recommendations [6]. Additionally, machine learning-based diabetic foot ulcer detection allows early intervention, and this further improves patient outcomes [7]. Although AI-based diabetes management has advanced significantly, harmony in integration is still a top wish for effective and overall long-term disease management.

III. METHODOLOGY

The suggested smartphone app is created on Flutter for frontend and Python for backend to monitor calorie intake, nutrition analysis, and artificial intelligence-driven diet recommendations with ease. It keeps track of medicine intake based on dosages, timing, and interaction with food and physical activity. It also examines the effects of exercise on blood glucose levels and suggests personalized exercise regimes based on the patient's requirement.

A predictive model using machine learning identifies risks of diabetic foot ulcers via sophisticated image processing, enabling early intervention. The system also features real-time alerts for critical conditions like hyperglycemia and hypoglycemia, enabling prompt medical intervention. AI-powered recommendations also streamline lifestyle decisions, increase treatment adherence, and maximize overall diabetes management. Using machine learning, predictive analytics, and real-time monitoring, the app provides proactive and personalized diabetes management.

A. Dataset

This study utilizes four diverse datasets for diabetic care and management. The Food Item Identification Dataset consists of approximately 5,000 images, covering 50 different food categories (healthy, moderate, and unhealthy foods), with each food category containing around 100 images. Secondly, the Foot Ulcer Prediction Dataset, consisting of around 3,500 images, includes three ulcer categories: High-Level, Medium-Level Foot Ulcers, and Normal Wounds, with each category containing approximately 1,200 images. These images are captured using a camera and sourced from Google's valid image datasets and other publicly available image collections [8]. The images were preprocessed to 224×224 pixels with $1/255$ rescaling normalization. Key parameters for this dataset include `IMAGE_SHAPE = (224, 224)`, batch size is 16, and an image size of 640 during training.

The Patient Dataset contains 4,000 records with critical data such as Fasting Blood Sugar (FBS), Post-Prandial Blood Sugar (PPBS), HbA1c, BMI, time of day, meal information, physical activity level, medication details, and initial diagnoses. These features serve as input variables to predict whether a patient is at risk of hyperglycemia or has normal blood sugar levels. This dataset is used to predict blood glucose levels and assess diabetes risk. Lastly, the Exercise Dataset includes 3,500 records, focusing on the impact of physical activity on blood glucose regulation. It contains attributes such as exercise type, duration, gender, BMI classification, diabetes status, and blood glucose levels before

and after exercise. This dataset is sourced from public health databases, including the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES) [9].

B. Preprocessing

The preprocessing involved resizing images to a consistent size of 224×224 pixels and normalizing them with $1/255$ rescaling to standardize input values across all datasets. For the Food Item Identification Dataset and Foot Ulcer Prediction Dataset, images were resized and normalized to ensure uniformity in input data. These datasets were divided into training, validation, and testing sets, with 80% used for training, 10% for validation, and 10% for testing.

For the Patient and Exercise Datasets, preprocessing included handling missing data and normalizing numerical values to standardize the input features [10]. To ensure compatibility with machine learning models, categorical variables were transformed into numerical formats through label encoding. This preprocessing step assigned unique integers to each category within a variable, enabling the models to interpret and process the data effectively. Following this transformation, the dataset was structured appropriately, facilitating consistent and efficient training across various data types.

C. Augmentation

Data augmentation was applied to both the Food Item Identification Dataset and Foot Ulcer Prediction Dataset to enhance model robustness and prevent overfitting. The augmentation techniques used included random rotation, horizontal flipping, zooming, shifting, and shearing. These transformations ensured that the model was exposed to a variety of image conditions, improving its ability to generalize new, unseen data. Augmentation is applied dynamically during the training process, allowing the model to learn from a broader variety of input variations without needing additional data collection [11]. This process helped to simulate diverse real-world conditions, which are crucial for better performance in real-world scenarios.

D. Model Architecture & Implementation

The proposed system incorporates various machine learning models to assist in diabetes care, such as food recognition, calorie estimation, foot ulcer risk assessment, hyperglycemia prediction, and activity suggestion. This section discusses the incorporation of these models and how they assist in the provision of personalized, proactive care.

1) Food Identification and Calorie Estimation System

The system employs YOLOv8 for food classification, utilizing a convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture optimized for real-time image recognition [12]. The architecture consists of three primary components: the backbone, which extracts key features from input images; the neck, which enhances, and fuses extracted features to create more complex representations; and the head, which performs the final classification based on these enhanced features. The model integrates deep convolutional layers with residual connections, which improve feature representation while maintaining computational efficiency. These residual connections mitigate the issue of vanishing gradients, enabling the training of deeper models and facilitating the

extraction of more abstract, meaningful features from the input data.

The implementation adopts a transfer learning approach by fine-tuning a pre-trained YOLOv8 classification model (yolo11n-cls.pt) on the dataset [13]. This method accelerates the training process, allowing the model to quickly adapt to the new dataset with fewer data samples and training epochs. Input images are resized to 224×224 pixels to standardize the dimensions, and pixel values are normalized by rescaling them using a factor of $1/255$, bringing the values within the range $[0, 1]$. Following the classification of the food item, calorie estimation is performed based on the food's weight, using the formula defined in (1),

$$C = W \times D \quad (1)$$

where C is the estimated calorie content, W is the portion size (in grams), and D is the caloric density (calories per gram). The portion size W is manually entered by the user, who measures the food using a weight scale before inputting the value. This manual input method is chosen to enhance accuracy, as automated portion estimation may introduce errors. The caloric density D is a predefined value for each food item. Once the food item is identified, the system multiplies the weight by the respective caloric density to provide the estimated calorie content.

Upon completing the training phase, the model is capable of classifying food items from images in real time. Input images are processed through the trained network, generating an output that identifies the food item category with the highest probability. After classification, the system proceeds with calorie estimation by multiplying the manually entered weight with its respective caloric density, ensuring improved precision over automated weight detection methods, which may occasionally yield inaccuracies. This approach allows the system to facilitate both food identification and calorie estimation in real time, ensuring reliable and efficient operation in dynamic environments.

2) Risk Level of Foot Ulcer Prediction System

The system utilizes MobileNetV2 for diabetic foot ulcer classification, leveraging a convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture optimized for mobile applications [12]. The architecture consists of three primary components: a backbone for extracting key features from input images, a neck for enhancing and fusing extracted features, and a head for performing final classification. The model integrates deep convolutional layers with residual connections to enhance feature representation, maintain computational efficiency, mitigate vanishing gradients, and enable deeper training for extracting more abstract and meaningful features. The model's backbone, pre-trained on ImageNet, is fine-tuned for classification by incorporating a Global Average Pooling layer, followed by a final Dense output layer with three units, each representing a distinct wound severity category. The classification is structured as follows: 0 for High-Level Foot Ulcers, 1 for Medium-Level Foot Ulcers, and 2 for Normal Wounds, ensuring precise categorization of wound severity and facilitating accurate diagnosis and intervention.

The implementation follows a transfer learning approach by fine-tuning a pre-trained MobileNetV2 classification model (mobilenet_v2_no_top.h5) on the dataset [14]. This

approach speeds up the training process, allowing the model to adapt efficiently to the new dataset with fewer samples and epochs. Input images are resized to 224×224 pixels to standardize the dimensions for consistency, and pixel values are normalized by rescaling them with a factor of $1/255$, ensuring they fall within the range $[0,1]$. The optimization process minimizes categorical cross-entropy loss as defined in Equation (2),

$$L = - \sum y_i \log(y^i) \quad (2)$$

where y_i is the true class label and y^i is the predicted probability. Model training and inference were performed using TensorFlow and Keras. The model was trained on a dataset of labeled foot ulcer images and validated on unseen images to ensure robust classification performance. Upon completing the training phase, the model is capable of classifying foot ulcers into distinct risk level categories. Input images are processed through the trained network, which generates an output corresponding to the risk level category with the highest predicted probability. This approach enables accurate risk assessment of foot ulcers, ensuring reliable and efficient operation in clinical and real-world environments.

3) System to Classify Risk of Hyperglycemia

In developing the Diabetic Risk Classification System, a comprehensive dataset was utilized, encompassing both numerical and categorical clinical features. The numerical variables included Fasting Blood Sugar (FBS), Post-Prandial Blood Sugar (PPBS), HbA1c levels, and BMI. The categorical variables comprised Time of Day, Meal Information, Physical Activity Level, Medication Information, and Diagnose.

As part of the preprocessing phase, categorical variables were converted into numerical form to ensure compatibility with machine learning algorithms. Once preprocessed, the dataset was divided into predictor variables (X) and the target variable (y). The predictor variables included the numerical features along with the encoded categorical data. The target variable, Diagnose, indicated the patient's classification regarding hyperglycemia risk. This structured input format ensured that the models received clean and interpretable data, enhancing prediction accuracy.

A dataset comprising 4,000 patient records was curated and split into training and testing sets to ensure proper validation. Multiple classification algorithms were implemented and assessed, including Random Forest, K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Logistic Regression, and Support Vector Classifier (SVC). Among these, the SVC model demonstrated superior performance due to its high generalization ability and effectiveness in managing complex, high-dimensional healthcare data [4, 15]. It is also noted that SVC is particularly suitable for medical applications where precision and reliability are critical, as it mitigates overfitting and ensures consistent accuracy across varied test scenarios [5].

The finalized SVC model was serialized using the Pickle module to enable real-time predictions. New patient inputs are fed into the system, and the model classifies the risk status as either "Normal" or "Risk of Hyperglycemia." The system's continued expansion and refinement of training data enhance its robustness and improve the accuracy of diabetes risk prediction.

4) Activity Management and Suggestion System

Machine Learning is employed within the Activity Management and Suggestion system to provide real-time personalized exercise recommendations for diabetic patients. This includes adjusting to the duration (continuation, increase, or reduction) of existing exercises, and delivering new workout guides from its internal activity library. Real-time user activity data, including exercise type, duration, , are processed alongside key health parameters such as gender, diabetes status, and blood glucose levels to generate optimal workout modifications tailored to individual health conditions.

The model architecture is composed of three core components: feature extraction, classification, and recommendation generation. Feature extraction involves gathering real-time user data (exercise type, duration, gender, diabetes status, and blood glucose levels), followed by preprocessing and normalization. For classification, both Decision Tree and Random Forest algorithms were evaluated, with Random Forest selected [16] for deployment due to its superior predictive accuracy. The implementation utilizes Scikit-learn 1.2.2, NumPy 1.24.3, Pandas 1.5.3, and Matplotlib 3.7.1, enabling the classification of exercise intensity based on personalized health indicators. In the final stage, the recommendation module evaluates blood glucose levels, step count, and calories burned to determine whether the patient should continue, modify, or stop the workout. The model represents the exercise adjustment prediction based on the Random Forest classifier, which is defined in Equation (3),

$$\hat{Y} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N f_i \quad (3)$$

where \hat{Y} predict exercise adjustment category (e.g., continue, increase, reduce), N represent the number of decision trees in the random forest, $f_i(X)$ is the output of the i -th decision tree for the input feature vector X . The feature vector X consists of parameters such as exercise type, duration, gender, diabetic status, and blood glucose levels. The trained model was serialized using pickle and integrated into an interactive user interface, enabling real-time predictions. This system ensures

adaptive and data-driven exercise management, helping diabetic patients maintain optimal physical activity levels.

Combining all components, the integrated system we proposed brings together multiple advanced models to provide comprehensive diabetic patient care. The system incorporates YOLOv8 for accurate food identification and calorie estimation, MobileNetV2 for predicting the risk of diabetic foot ulcers, a Random Forest classifier for generating personalized exercise recommendations, and a Support vector classifier for classifying blood glucose levels. Fig. 1 illustrates the complete architecture of the proposed system.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Food Identification and Calorie Estimation System

The results demonstrate the effectiveness of the YOLOv8 model in accurately classifying meal images. The model demonstrates strong performance, achieving 91.3% training accuracy and 90.3% testing accuracy, indicating its capability to effectively learn and generalize across different food items. These accuracy levels highlight the model's reliability in distinguishing various food types, ensuring consistent and precise identification in real-world applications.

The system's performance is further validated using key accuracy metrics such as Top 1 and Top 5 accuracy. Top 1 accuracy indicates how often the model's most confident prediction matches the correct food label, while Top 5 accuracy shows whether the correct label appears within the model's top five predictions, useful in cases where multiple food items appear visually similar. These metrics confirm the model's strong classification capability across diverse food categories. Additionally, the system is optimized for real-time use, with preprocessing taking 84.2 ms, inference 248.8 ms, and post-processing just 0.1 ms. This efficient performance ensures smooth and practical deployment in real-world, dynamic environments.

To further enhance reliability, the system displays only high-confidence predictions, reducing the risk of incorrect classifications. Fig. 2. presents a sample classification output, showcasing the system's ability to accurately identify food items.

Fig. 1. Architectural Framework of the System.

Fig. 2. Sample Meal Classification Output Using YOLOv8.

Currently, the system is implemented for a selected range of food items, categorized as follows: Single-item foods such as apple, carrot, donut, boiled egg, and ice cream. Meal-based foods such as fried rice, noodles, caesar salad, hotdog, and kottu. At this stage, food identification and calorie estimation are limited to these predefined categories. However, future advancements can enhance the system to recognize a broader variety of food items, including complex and multi-component meals, improving their overall applicability.

Table 1 provides data for the above-mentioned food items, offering a clear estimate of the caloric content based on the provided portion sizes and predefined caloric density. Please note that the portion sizes listed are manually entered based on current measurements and may vary based on portion sizes or individual preferences.

TABLE I. SAMPLE FOOD CALORIE ESTIMATION TABLE

Food Item	Caloric Density (Cal/g)	Portion Size (g)	Estimated Calorie (Cal)
Apple	0.52	182	95
Carrot	0.41	61	25
Donut	4.21	60	253
Boiled Egg	1.56	50	78
Ice Cream	2.07	100	207
Fried Rice	1.63	200	326
Noodles	1.4	150	210
Caesar Salad	1.6	200	320
HotDog	2.9	52	151
Kottu	1.9	200	380

These results highlight the efficiency and reliability of the YOLOv8-based classification system in meal recognition. When integrated into a healthcare application, this system provides diabetic and prediabetic patients with real-time dietary insights, enabling informed and personalized nutritional decisions. The combination of high classification accuracy and rapid inference speed ensures that the system is well-suited for real-world dietary management applications.

B. Risk Level of Foot Ulcer Prediction System

The MobileNetV2-based model demonstrates strong performance in classifying foot ulcer risk levels, achieving a training accuracy of 91.54% and an overall testing accuracy of 88%. These results indicate the model's robust generalization capability, with notable performance across three categories: High-Level Foot Ulcers, Medium-Level Foot Ulcers, and Normal Wounds. The classification metrics further support these findings, showing consistently high precision, recall, and F1-score values for each class. These metrics highlight the model's ability to effectively differentiate between ulcer severity levels with reliable accuracy. Table 2 provides a summary of the testing-related metrics, including classification accuracy, precision, recall, and the F1 score for each class.

TABLE II. CLASSIFICATION OF WOUND AND ULCER DETECTION

Class	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
High-Level Foot Ulcers	0.88	0.83	0.71	0.77
Medium Level Foot Ulcers	0.88	0.80	0.92	0.86
Normal Wounds	0.88	1.00	0.92	0.96

These results highlight the efficiency, robustness, and reliability of the MobileNetV2-based classification system in predicting foot ulcer risk levels. The system provides reliable assessments to support healthcare providers in clinical decision-making while also assisting diabetic and prediabetic patients by delivering timely risk evaluations. When integrated into a healthcare application, it enables proactive and personalized foot care management, enhancing both diagnostic accuracy and patient outcomes. Fig. 3. Shows a sample prediction output illustrating the system's capability to accurately classify the risk level of a foot ulcer based on an image.

Fig. 3. Sample Prediction Output of the Risk Level of Foot Ulcers.

C. System to Classify Risk of Having Hyperglycemia

The Diabetic Risk Classification System leverages machine learning techniques to predict whether a patient is at risk of Hyperglycemia or falls within the normal range based on clinical data. The system utilizes key health indicators, including Fasting Blood Sugar (FBS), Post-Prandial Blood Sugar (PPBS), HbA1c, BMI, time of day, meal information, physical activity level, medication details, and initial diagnoses. Categorical features such as Time of Day, Meal Information, Physical Activity Level, and Medication Information are encoded using Label Encoding to enhance model performance.

The dataset, comprising 4000 records, was split into training and testing sets for model development. Support Vector Classifier (SVC) was trained, achieving an accuracy of 93.36%. The confusion matrix analysis confirms that the SVC model effectively classifies both Normal and hyperglycemia cases with high reliability. The precision and recall values indicate a well-balanced classification, minimizing both false positives and negatives. Table 3 classifies the performance metrics for the risk of hyperglycemia and normal.

TABLE III. PERFORMANCE METRICS FOR HYPERGLYCEMIA

Class	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Risk Of Hyperglycemia	0.93	0.95	0.92	0.94
Normal	0.93	0.92	0.94	0.93

With an F1-score of 0.94, the model demonstrates strong predictive capabilities for diabetic risk assessment. These results highlight the system's potential to support healthcare professionals in early risk detection, clinical decision-making, and patient management. To facilitate real-time diabetes risk

classification, the trained SVC model is saved using Pickle, ensuring its availability for future use.

D. Activity Management and Suggestion System

The Activity Suggestion module was developed to monitor thorough activity tracking, including steps, distance, burned calories, and duration by integrating data from phone sensors such as accelerometer, pedometer, and GPS tracker. This module utilizes this recorded data, considering user-specific attributes such as exercise type, gender, BMI, and diabetes status, to offer personalized recommendations leveraging Decision Trees and Random Forest classifiers. The Random Forest Classifier demonstrated superior performance compared to the Decision Tree model, achieving an accuracy of 91.1%. It exhibited a high overall classification performance, with a weighted F1-score of 90%. The model achieved strong precision scores for "Continue" (90%), "Increase Duration" (90%), and "Stop" (91%). Table 4 classifies the exercise recommendation provided by the machine learning model based on the given health parameters.

TABLE IV. CLASSIFICATION OF EXERCISE IMPACT ON BLOOD GLUCOSE LEVELS

Activity Type	Time (min)	Gender	Diabetes Status	Blood Glucose	Result
Running	80	Female	Type 2	91	Continue
Cycling	40	Male	Type 2	137	Increase Duration
Zumba	91	Male	Type 1	169	Continue
Weightlifting	23	Male	Type 2	156	Decrease Intensity

Model classified exercise recommendations into a few categories based on the user's health parameters. Continue suggests maintaining the current routine as it is beneficial and poses no risks. Stop advises halting exercise due to potential health concerns, such as drastic changes in blood glucose levels. Decrease Intensity recommends lowering the weights used to prevent overexertion or adverse effects. Increasing duration encourages extending exercise time to achieve better health benefits when current activity levels are insufficient. In conjunction with these recommendations, the system provides exercise guides from its internal library to assist users in optimizing their workouts.

These results indicate that the Random Forest model exhibits superior performance in providing exercise recommendations and the potential of machine learning models in enhancing personalized activity management, which is crucial for optimizing health outcomes in diabetic patients. Additionally, the real-time tracking and visual feedback enhances user engagement, encouraging individuals to stay active and monitor their fitness goals effectively. However, the model currently does not consider external factors such as sleep quality or stress levels, which could further enhance personalization. Future improvements could incorporate these additional physiological parameters to refine the recommendation.

V. CONCLUSION

This research presents a comprehensive mobile application framework aimed at enhancing diabetes care through the integration of predictive analytics, AI-powered

monitoring, and real-time health insights. By incorporating modules for food identification, calorie estimation, foot ulcer risk detection, blood glucose level prediction, and personalized exercise recommendations, the system offers a unified solution to address the multifaceted needs of diabetic patients. The results demonstrate high accuracy and efficiency across all modules, confirming the system's capability to support proactive and personalized healthcare for diabetic patients.

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